

Understanding mitochondria's role in memory formation

Type: Symposium

Theme selection

Topic & Theme:

- G. Disorders of the Nervous System
- G.2: Alzheimer’s disease and other dementias

Details

Brief Description: Every year, an average of 23,000 people in Finland are diagnosed with new memory disorders. In 2040, it is estimated that there will be around 247,000 people with memory disorders in Finland, provided that the age-group-specific morbidity rate remains as it is today. **Mitochondria are emerging as biomarkers for early detection and monitoring of Alzheimer's disease progression** We therefore aim with this symposium to further discuss recent findings about mitochondria and memory disorders.

Objectives: It is believed that a healthy pool of mitochondria not only supports neuronal activity by providing enough energy supply and other related mitochondrial functions to neurons, but also guards neurons by minimizing mitochondrial related oxidative damage. Healthy mitochondria are critical for providing sufficient energy to maintain endogenous neuroprotective and reparative mechanisms, while disturbances in mitochondrial function, motility, fission, and fusion lead to neuronal malfunction and degeneration associated with excess free radical production and reduced intracellular calcium buffering.

It is hypothesised that *maintaining healthy mitochondrial function could be key to preserving memory* and social behavior. Mitochondria can be affected by ions

such as iron. In other words we need to be aware of the water we are drinking and how much iron it contains.

We aim to discuss how training(good muscle health) and food and water quality can keep your mitochondria healthy as well as pointing out stuff that damage your mitochondria.

We also aim to further discuss the impact of cold water therapy on the amount and health of mitochondria.

Diversity Statement: General public is not so familiar about mitochondria. We aim to include a MOOC about mitochondria that can be used before attending the symposium so everyone attending the symposium has an up to date knowledge about mitochondria. The MOOC will be free for everyone so even if you are not attending the symposium you will have access to an up to date information about mitochondria

Chair 1

Last name: Lindqvist

First name: Maria

Affiliation: Freelance

Speaker(s):

First name	Last name	Presentation Title	Gender	Career Status	Affiliation	City	Country	Publication
Maria	Lindqvist	Mitochondria's role in memory disorders	Woman	PI	Uppsala University	Stockholm	Sweden	Thesis: Maria Lindqvist 2008 Title: Wnt signaling affects cell adhesion and neuronal differentiation!
to be announced	to be announced	Microscopy and mitochondria	Prefer not to disclose	to be announced	to be announced	work in progress	Finland	to be announced
to be announced	to be announced	Mitochondria and metabolism	Prefer not to disclose	work in progress	work in progress	to be announced	Finland	to be announced
to be announced	work in progress	Mitochondria and cold	Prefer not to disclose	work in progress	digital	work in progress	Finland	to be announced

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